

Another Argument Towards Inequivallence of Complexity Classes

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ABSTRACT

As we have proposed our conjecture or hypothesis, we give the full disproof of this fact in this work.

INTRODUCTION

“P versus NP” theorem has a long-lasting history as we know [1], some of mathematical hypotheses are well presented before [2, 3, 4].

Our hypothesis was presented in [5].

DISPROOF

Our hypothesis gives the statement of Parallel Computation Law which states that there are no machine which could solve NP-complete problem in polynomial time, since the number of verifying and searching threads isn't limited:

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{NP}{N} = P \Rightarrow NP = N \cdot P,$$

where N is a number of threads and symbols P and NP are polynomial and non-polynomial problems.

CONCLUSION

We have given the full disproof of our functional hypothesis or conjecture stating the Parallel Computation Law (PCL) or Rabin-Scott Law.

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